

CLASSIFICATION AND PROPERTIES OF THREE-DIMENSIONAL TEXTILE PREFORMS

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Keywords: 3D textile preform, Representative geometric unit, Geometric properties, Mechanical properties

ABSTRACT

The three-dimensional (3D) textile preforms were used as the reinforcing phase of the textile structural composites, and its geometry effected the physical and mechanical properties of the composites. In this paper, the 3D textile preforms were classified, and three representative geometric units (RGUs) were proposed, namely orthogonal geometric unit, skew geometric unit and curved geometric unit. Other units were combinations and derivations of these three RGUs. The relationship and performance characterization of three RGUs were discussed. The concepts of rigid structure, flexible structure and elastoplastic structure were proposed. The fiber volume fraction, strength and strain characteristics of different structural preforms were predicted. The classification of 3D textile preforms was conducive to the relationship between geometries and performances, forming a technical system, and providing a theoretical basis for the selection of composites with different properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

Textile structural composites were advanced composites with textile preforms as the reinforcing phase. Textile preforms were made up of multiple fiber bundles in which the fiber bundles were distributed in multi-direction and closely interweaved through different processing. Textile structural composites could be divided into two-dimensional (2D) and three-dimensional (3D) textile structural composites according to the yarns in the thickness direction of textile preforms. 3D textile preforms have been used as the reinforcing phase of the textile structural composites, and their geometry influenced the physical and mechanical properties of the composites [1]. 3D textile composites, overcoming the low interlaminar mechanical properties of laminar composites, have become an important branch of high-performance composites. The meso-structure and mechanical properties of 3D textile preforms have been extensively studied in recent decades [2-4].

The classification of 3D textile preforms is conducive to understand the relationship between geometries and performances, forming a technical system, and providing a theoretical basis for the selection of composites with different properties. According to the manufacturing techniques basically developed from the traditional textile process, the 3D preforms mainly include 3D woven preforms, 3D knitted preforms, 3D braided preforms and 3D stitched preforms [5-7]. Bilisik reviewed the impact resistance of 2D fabrics and 3D preforms and ballistic structures. The classification of 3D preforms used as basic ballistic structure was outlined, it contained: 3D non-interlaced fabric, multi-stitched 3D woven fabric, 3D fully interlaced woven fabric, 3D orthogonal woven fabric, multiaxis 3D woven fabric, 3D braided fabric, 3D nonwoven fabric [8]. The advanced 3D spacer composites were classified based on the different factors depending on the orientation of the yarn, the yarn sets and the geometry [9]. 3D orthogonal layer to layer and through the thickness woven structures with different interlocking patterns, used as preforms in green composites were presented [10]. Based on type of

interlacement patterns, yarn orientation and number of yarn sets, 3D braided preforms were divided into three categories, namely 3D braid, 3D axial braid and multi-axis 3D braid, which were non-interlaced inside. 3D braided and woven preforms were classified based on various parameters depending on the yarn sets, yarn orientation and intertwining, micro-meso unit cells and macro geometry [3, 11-13]. By describing the textile preforms with point group and space group, the geometric structures of preforms could be derived and classified reasonably and effectively, so that the types of the textile preform were no longer limited to process distinction. Based on the space group theory, the geometric structure of the braided composites could be deduced, and provided a systematic and effective mathematical method for the development of textile preforms. It could greatly enrich the varieties of 3D braided materials and optimize the performance of the braided composites [14-16]. However, preforms with the same structure could be realized by different processes, which could hardly meet the development requirements of high-performance composites according to process classification. In addition, it is not conducive to the construction and research of the relationship between structure and properties.

3D textile composites possessed the periodic microstructure, and the macroscopic mechanical behaviors of composites were affected by geometric factors such as fiber volume fraction, shape and distribution of composites. Numerical models on different length scales were developed that capture the mechanical behavior of preforms and their composites. The representative volume method and the asymptotic homogenization method were two numerical methods for predicting the equivalent mechanical properties of periodic materials. Therefore, scholars at home and abroad have done a lot of researches on the models. Models of 3D woven composites were classified into continuum macro-scale approaches and discrete models [17]. The studies relevant to the structural modeling of 3D braided preforms have been classified into three types, i.e., mechanical equivalence models, unit cell geometrical models and yarn geometrical models [18]. Meso-geometric models which directly influenced the precision of numerical results were also elaborated [19-21]. Whereas, many kinds of models and calculation methods were proposed. Without the characteristics of universality and generality, it could not form a technical system.

In this paper, the 3D textile preforms have been classified, and three RGUs were proposed. The relevance and performance characterizations of three RGUs have been discussed. The concepts of rigid structure, flexible structure and elastoplastic structure have been defined. The fiber volume fraction, strength and strain characteristics of different structural preforms have been predicted.

2 THREE REPRESENTATIVE GEOMETRIC UNITS

Representative volume element was a mathematical concept. The scale of macroscopic level was relative to that of mesoscopic level. For different materials, the size and length of representative volume element were different. 3D textile preforms were a kind of fiber bundle collections with periodicity and anisotropy. The representative volume element was usually used to discuss the meso-geometric structure of the preforms.

Fig. 1 Three representative geometric units.

In view of the numbers, distribution, interweave mode and the complexity of fibers in 3D textile preforms, the RGUs have been divided into three types namely, orthogonal geometric unit, curved geometric unit and skew geometric unit. The three RGUs have been described separately in Fig.1. The

shape of these RGUs is postulated to hexahedron. Set l, w, h as the length, width and height separately. As shown in Fig. 1(d), the volume of RGUs is

$$U = lwh \quad (1)$$

2.1 The orthogonal geometric unit

The yarns in orthogonal units are along the Cartesian coordinate. As shown in the Fig.1(a), the yarns in the RGUs are supposed to be straight. In the internal RGUs of the 3D textile preforms, the directions of the yarns are mainly distributed in the three axes directions. The yarns could be divided into three groups according to the axes, and the angle between each two groups is 90 degree. The yarns along z direction are perpendicular to x -directional yarns in xoz plan. Meanwhile, the z -directional yarns are perpendicular to y -directional yarns in yoz plan. There is no other types of yarns except the three groups mentioned above. The matrixes of these three group yarns is

$$M_x = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, M_y = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, M_z = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

The ablation-resistant and heat-resistant properties of composites are positively correlated with the fiber volume fraction of preforms. Fiber volume fraction refers to the volume of reinforcing fibers per unit volume of composite materials. The fiber volume of orthogonal unit is

$$U_f = S_l n_l l + S_w n_w w + S_h n_h h \quad (3)$$

Where S_l, S_w and S_h are the area of group yarns separately; n_l, n_w and n_h are the number of each group yarns.

The fiber volume fraction of orthogonal unit is

$$V_f = \frac{U_f}{U} \times 100\% \quad (4)$$

2.2 The curved geometric unit

The curved geometric unit contained the buckling yarns in the minimum representative volume element. Due to the buckling yarns, the proportion of unit fibers could be adjusted adaptively to suit the unit size. Fig. 1(b) showed a kind of curved geometric unit, and the unit contained the buckling yarns, including or excluding straight lines.

Fig. 2 The geometric parameters of buckling yarns.

In order to predict the fiber volume fraction of curved geometric unit, the length of buckling yarns must be calculated. The length of buckling yarns in the unit are supposed to three parts. Set l_1 and l_3 express the arc length of buckling yarns, α expresses the direction of the buckling yarns, and β is the

central angle of l_1 and l_3 . l_2 expresses the straight length, as shown in Fig. 2. Many assumptions are established to analyze the meso-geometric structure of the buckling yarns. The axis shape is regarded as regular shapes such as arc, sinusoid, etc., and irregular shapes by slice observation. The volume of buckling yarns is

$$U_c = n_c S_c \times (l_1 + l_2 + l_3) \quad (5)$$

Where S_c is the yarn cross-sectional area; n_c is the number of buckling yarns in the unit.

The type of yarns in the curved geometric unit must contain the buckling yarn, and it may contain one or more group yarns in the orthogonal unit. Then the fiber volume in the curved geometric unit could be calculated according to the equation (3). According to the above equations, the fiber volume fraction of this type unit could be finally deduced. Based on calculus theory, the differential treatment of the buckling yarn was carried out, and then the matrix representation of the buckling yarn was calculated by integrating the length of the yarn. Both considering the straight and buckling yarns, the elastic constants of this unit could be predicted.

2.3 The skew geometric unit

The yarns in skew geometric unit are assumed that the distributions are in a straight line and form a certain angle in space. A kind of skew geometric unit is shown in Fig. 1(c), and the number of yarn segments is uncertain. The representation of single yarn segment in space coordinate is illustrated in Fig.3, and the geometrical parameters of the yarns are explained. The directional angles of single yarn segment in space coordinate are set as α' and β' . The local coordinate system is $o'-123$, the yarn length direction is 1 axis, and the transverse isotropic plane of yarns is $o'-23$ plane. The angle between 1 axis and x axis is β' , and α' is the angle between the yarn projection on the $yo'z$ plane and y axis. The length of single yarn segment is l_s , which is a function with geometric parameters.

Fig. 3 The yarn segment in space coordinate.

For any yarn segment in space, it could be assumed to be transversely isotropic composite materials. The length of single yarn segment could be deduced by the geometric parameters, as well as the other yarns in this unit. The unit could be regarded as the combination of single yarns. The shape of yarn cross-section is supposed to different geometrical shape. The volume of fibers in skew unit is

$$U_s = S_s n_s l_s \quad (6)$$

Where S_s is the cross-sectional area of yarns, and yarn cross-sectional shapes in different units are different; n_s is the number of yarn segments.

According to the equations, the fiber volume and geometric parameters of the skew geometric unit could be predicted. The matrix representation of the yarns in this unit could be deduced by effective numerical analysis methods.

3 THE RELATIONSHIP OF THE THREE RGU

The meso-structure and transformation of the fibers affect the performance of the preforms, which in turn affects the properties of 3D textile composites. According to the geometric properties of textile fibers, the relationship of these three RGUs was discussed in this part. The properties of these three RGU were analyzed in this section.

The properties of fibers in preforms were mainly characterized by the directions and curvatures of the textile yarns. As shown in Fig. 4, two coordinate axes expressed the two properties of the fibers in preforms. In the horizontal axis, the direction of the fibers was from unidirectional fibers to multi-directional fibers. The property of the fibers in vertical axis was from low-curvature to high curvature.

Fig. 4 The connection of three RGUs.

The orthogonal geometric unit was distributed in the quadrant of unidirectional fiber and low-curvature. Obviously, the performance of fibers in the orthogonal geometric unit proposed less-orientation and low-curvature. The fibers in orthogonal geometric unit were perpendicular to each other, and ‘pin-and-column’ consolidation could distribute the external force evenly and transmit it to the internal unit. It was characterized by ‘rigidity’ of the whole composites.

The curved geometric unit possessed high flexibility owing to the buckling yarns in the unit. Therefore, this type of unit could be distributed in the quadrant with multidirectional and high-curvature. The length of ‘buckling’ of linear fibers under the external function of curved bending fibers could change with the shape. Removed the external function, the element restraint was difficult to recover, showing a ‘flexible’ feature.

The skew geometric unit was arranged in the quadrant with multi-directional and low-curvature as shown in Fig. 4. Linear fibers in the skew geometric unit bend under external pressure, and the external function transferred to diagonally distributed fibers in the unit. The interlacing points in the unit was characterized by ‘elastic-plastic’ deformation and displacement.

Fig. 5 The genomic assemblies of these RGUs.

In addition to these three representative geometric units, the other unit types were also existed in 3D textile preforms. The other unit types could be regarded as the combination and derived of these three units. The other units were composed of two or three afore-mentioned units. As shown in Fig. 5, the final unit was obtained by the two types of the three representative geometric units. The other units of 3D textile preform could be regarded as the ‘genomic assemblies’ of basic characteristics of these three RGUs. The fiber volume fraction effected the properties of 3D textile preforms, and the value of other units could be predicted based on the above equations. The mechanical properties, which deduced by the geometric structures, also presented the combination of these different unit properties.

4 3D TEXTILE PREFORMS

The definition of rigid structure, flexible structure and elastoplastic structure have been proposed in this section. These three structural preforms corresponding to the three RGUs were classified. The connection of the units and preforms has been expressed. 3D orthogonal preform, angle-interlock preform and four-step braided preform were introduced to further explain the classification of 3D textile preforms, as shown in Fig. 6. These representative structures were composed of the relevant geometric units, and the structure possessed the characteristic mechanical properties.

Fig. 6 The relevance of three RGUs and preforms.

The single yarns of composite materials are supposed as transversely isotropic material. As shown in Fig. 3, the global coordinate system x - y - z and the local coordinate system 1-2-3 are expressed. Set the 2-3 coordinate plane is isotropic and the 1 axis is perpendicular to the 2-3 coordinate plane. The stiffness matrix of any yarn segment in space is

$$[C_f] = \begin{pmatrix} c_{11} & c_{12} & c_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ c_{12} & c_{22} & c_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ c_{13} & c_{23} & c_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & c_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & c_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & c_{66} \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Where c_{ij} ($i, j=1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6$) are the nine independent constants.

The off-axis stiffness matrix $[C_f']$ is

$$[C_f'] = [A][C_f][A]^T \quad (8)$$

$[A]$ is Hamiltonian stress transformation matrix,

$$[A] = \begin{pmatrix} l_1^2 & m_1^2 & n_1^2 & 2m_1n_1 & 2n_1l_1 & 2l_1m_1 \\ l_2^2 & m_2^2 & n_2^2 & 2m_2n_2 & 2n_2l_2 & 2l_2m_2 \\ l_3^2 & m_3^2 & n_3^2 & 2m_3n_3 & 2n_3l_3 & 2l_3m_3 \\ l_2l_3 & m_2m_3 & n_2n_3 & m_2n_3 + m_3n_2 & n_2l_3 + n_3l_2 & l_2m_3 + l_3m_2 \\ l_3l_1 & m_3m_1 & n_3n_1 & m_3n_1 + m_1n_3 & n_3l_1 + n_1l_3 & l_3m_1 + l_1m_3 \\ l_1l_2 & m_1m_2 & n_1n_2 & m_1n_2 + m_2n_1 & n_1l_2 + n_2l_1 & l_1m_2 + l_2m_1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

l_i, m_i, n_i are the direction cosine of the angle between the local coordinate 1-2-3 and the global coordinate axis x - y - z . It is obtained

$$\begin{cases} l_1 = \cos \beta' & l_2 = \sin \beta' \cos \alpha' & l_3 = \sin \beta' \sin \alpha' \\ m_1 = 0 & m_2 = \sin \alpha' & m_3 = -\cos \alpha' \\ n_1 = -\sin \beta' & n_2 = \cos \beta' \cos \alpha' & n_3 = \cos \beta' \sin \alpha' \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

4.1 The rigid structure

The preforms of rigid structure were mainly formed by the orthogonal geometric units. As a representation of rigid structure, 3D orthogonal preforms were linearly arranged. The symmetry structure and straight fibers of the preforms made the excellent properties of the composites.

The yarns along the axes could be regarded as the transversely isotropic materials. The angle between the coordinate could be obtained obviously. The orientation angles of the yarns along x -axis are $\alpha' = \pi/2, \beta' = 0$, Hamiltonian stress transformation matrix is $[A_l]$. Similarly, along the y -axis, $\alpha' = 0, \beta' = \pi/2$ and $[A_w]$ are obtained; along the z -axis, $\alpha' = \pi/2, \beta' = \pi/2$ and $[A_h]$ are deduced. The stiffness matrix of rigid structure is

$$[C_r] = \frac{l[A_l][C_f][A_l]^T + w[A_w][C_f][A_w]^T + h[A_h][C_f][A_h]^T}{l + w + h} \quad (11)$$

4.2 The flexible structure

The flexible structural preforms are constituted by major curved geometric units. The yarns in flexible structures are unidirectional fiber bundles with variable orientation, and its stiffness matrix has a functional relationship with spatial coordinates. According to the stiffness averaging method, the stiffness matrix of buckling yarns is expressed by the average integral value of the element to the yarn length L .

$$[C_f]_L = \frac{1}{L} \int [A][C_f][A]^T dL \quad (12)$$

The global stiffness matrix of flexible structure is deduced by using the fiber volume fraction of different group yarns. The global stiffness matrix is

$$[C_c] = V_c [C_f]_L + V_r [C_r] \quad (13)$$

Where V_c is the fiber volume fraction of buckling yarns; V_r is the fiber volume fraction of straight yarns in curved geometric unit.

4.3 The elastoplastic structure

The preforms with elastoplastic structure were composed of skew geometric units. The multi-directional skew structure possessed elastic-plastic property, the number of increasing and decreasing units of the special-shaped yarn bundle was discontinuous, and the corresponding point was abrupt elastic-plastic property.

The stiffness matrix of yarns in elastoplastic structure is

$$[C_s] = \frac{1}{n} V_s \sum_{j=1}^n [D]_j [A] [C_f] [A]^T [D]_j^T \quad (14)$$

Where $[D]_j$ is the translation transformation matrix between two yarn segments, and the matrix could be deduced by the space group theory [14].

4.4 The relationship of three representative structures

The mechanical property of 3D textile composites was mainly decided by the geometric structure of the preforms. There was a certain relationship among these geometric structures, as shown in Fig 7. The preform in the initial statement was the flexible structure, and the curved yarns in the unit had the larger curvature. With the increase of force, the buckling yarns gradually straightened up to the straight yarns in the elastoplastic structures. Finally, the preform was turned to the rigid structure.

Fig. 7 The relationship of three representative structures.

5 RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

The classification of 3D textile preforms was reviewed in this paper. A new method to classify the preforms was proposed, and three RGUs have been identified. The geometric structures and properties of these units were discussed. The relationship of the three RGUs have been studied based on the fiber properties. In this paper, the relevance of three RGUs and 3D textile preforms was analysed. The definition of rigid structure, flexible structure and elastoplastic structure have been identified. The geometric structure of above preforms have been predicted. The mechanical properties of three structural preforms have been discussed.

The structural characteristics of other preforms could be regarded as the assembly of these three RGU. The future research direction is aimed to obtain the new structural preforms to satisfy the demand in engineering, and the related properties will be studied with the topological methods. Applied research on basic features of new preforms will be carried out. The influence of basic characteristics of RGUs on the performance of composite process will be studied. The relationship between the basic characteristics of RGUs and the mechanical properties of materials will be further discussed.

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